

DEVELOPMENT AND USAGE AREAS OF EDUCATIONAL DIGITAL MATERIAL IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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With technological advances and artificial intelligence tools infiltrating every aspect of our lives at a dizzying pace and inevitably becoming indispensable elements of individuals of all ages even in our daily lives, we have become surrounded by technological devices such as televisions, smartphones, tablets, computers, and game consoles. Even very young children can easily use these devices and are intensively exposed to screen-based content (Kabali et al., 2015). Research on children's use of digital tools shows that in the United States, 84% of children between the ages of 2-4 use digital tools for an average of 2.5 hours a day (Rideout & Robb, 2020); in Turkey, 76.1% of children use smartphones and the rate of internet use has increased to 91.3% (TÜİK, 2024). In the literature, it is stated that children mostly use digital tools to play games, watch videos, participate in e-learning activities, use search engines or just make phone calls. Today, artificial intelligence tools have been added to these uses.

The widespread access of children to digital tools brings with it various debates. While on the one hand, well-prepared digital content supports the development of children's imagination, creativity and higher-order thinking skills; on the other hand, it can increase attention and sleep problems and the risk of obesity. One of the most important activities of children on digital tools is online games and social media channels (Kabali et al., 2015); exposure to inappropriate content on such platforms increases the likelihood of violence and abuse.

The increasing integration of technology in education has made it possible to support learning processes in preschool through digital materials. Preschool education is a critical period of children's cognitive, social and emotional development and the use of appropriate pedagogical tools during this period is decisive in increasing learning outcomes (Haugland, 2000). Research shows that digital materials are effective in attracting preschool children's attention and increasing their motivation (Neumann, 2018). Interactive digital tools support cognitive development processes by allowing children to have multi-sensory experiences (Papadakis & Fragkouli, 2020). For example, tablet-based educational applications have been found to positively affect children's problem-solving skills, language development and understanding of early mathematical concepts (Zheng, 2016).

The fact that educational digital materials offer individualized learning environments enables children to access content that is appropriate for their learning speed and style. This enables the provision of support appropriate to the child's developmental level within the scope of Vygotsky's “Zone of Proximal Development” theory (Vygotsky, 1978). In addition, the instant feedback mechanisms provided by digital materials increase self-regulation and error awareness in learning processes (Rogers et al., 2019). However, it is emphasized in the literature that the effective use of digital materials can be possible with content design based on pedagogical foundations (Plowman & Stephen, 2005). The development of age-appropriate, interactive and entertaining content enables children to use digital materials more efficiently (Kucirkova, 2019). In addition, the guidance of

parents and educators increases the impact of digital materials and supports the development of children's digital literacy skills (Neumann & Neumann, 2014).

The use of digital materials in preschool education contributes to the development of technological literacy at an early age and provides enriched learning environments that support cognitive and social development. However, selecting and implementing these materials in line with the principles of pedagogical accuracy, age appropriateness and adult guidance is critical to the effectiveness of the learning process. When preschool teachers design digital materials taking into account children's developmental characteristics, these materials become not only technological tools but also teaching resources with high pedagogical value. Research shows that teachers' conscious and planned integration of educational technologies enriches children's learning experiences and provides lasting learning (Yelland, 2005; Donohue & Schomburg, 2017).

Digital Materials and Their Educational Contributions

Digital materials are contents that support teaching and learning processes, designed and presented in digital environment. These materials include tools such as educational software, mobile applications, digital storybooks, interactive whiteboards, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR) applications and video content (Couse & Chen, 2010). Types of Educational Digital Materials; Educational Games: Game-based learning supports learning by feeding children's natural curiosity (Plass, Homer & Kinzer, 2015); Mobile Apps: Interactive applications develop motor skills and problem-solving abilities, especially in 3-6 year olds (Neumann & Neumann, 2014); Animations and Videos: Effective in concept teaching and attention development (Linebarger & Piotrowski, 2009); Digital Storybooks: Support language development, early literacy and narrative skills (Shamir & Korat, 2007).

Digital materials make multifaceted contributions to children's cognitive, language, social-emotional and psychomotor development in early childhood. However, in order for these contributions to emerge, the materials should be used in accordance with the developmental level of the child, based on pedagogical foundations and purposeful (NAEYC & Fred Rogers Center, 2012). In particular, interactive games and software improve children's ability to analyze, establish cause-effect relationships and reasoning skills (Clements & Sarama, 2007). Such applications contribute to children's attention span, problem solving skills and conceptual development. In a study conducted by Zomer-Ploeg et al. (2020), it was shown that digital applications are effective in learning basic concepts such as numbers, measurement and sequencing. Mind-building games such as tangrams, digital puzzles and logic games support higher-order thinking skills (Papadakis et al., 2018). Audio stories, interactive books and digital storytelling applications contribute to language and communication skills by increasing children's vocabulary, narrative construction skills and language awareness (Shamir & Korat, 2007; Zucker et al., 2009). In their research, Korat and Shamir (2007) showed that e-books support children's vocabulary learning and text comprehension skills more than traditional books. Digital Storybooks support both listening and visual reading skills by presenting text and images simultaneously with the stories being read, while Audio Apps increase sensitivity to basic components of language such as phonological awareness, rhythm and intonation. Group-work versions of the digital materials encourage interaction and collaboration among children. Moreover, the skills of recognizing emotions, empathy and self-regulation can be developed through digital stories and role-playing games (Edwards, 2005). Collaborative Digital Games develop children's social skills such as sharing, turn-taking and decision-making as they complete tasks together. Emotion Recognition Applications such as matching facial expressions support the development of

emotional intelligence. Bers (2020) emphasizes that children's social-emotional learning experiences can be strengthened through digital games, but this should be supported by teacher guidance. Digital tools also make significant contributions to psycho-motor development. In particular, touch screens and motion-based technologies (e.g. tablets, smart boards, X-BOX and WEE games) support the development of children's fine motor and gross motor skills (Couse & Chen, 2010). Hourcade et al. (2015) showed that tablet use is effective in developing hand skills, especially in children aged 3-5 years. In addition to all these, it also makes important contributions to creativity and creative expression skills. The unstructured and open-ended nature of digital applications that support creativity allows children to learn through their own preferences and offers new ways to express their original thoughts (Bird & Edwards, 2015). In particular, coding, story creation and digital art applications support children's creative thinking skills (Resnick, 2017). Scratch Jr and similar programs teach children algorithmic thinking through story building and character control, while audio and visual content generation tools allow children to express their own ideas in a digital environment.

The Role of Teachers and Digital Pedagogy

The effective use of digital materials in preschool education is closely related to teachers' pedagogical knowledge and attitudes towards technology integration (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Teachers are not only the users of digital tools, but also the active actors who guide children, select materials according to their purpose, and collaborate with families. In order for teachers to use digital tools effectively, it is necessary to increase their digital literacy and to include digital pedagogical content in pre-service and in-service trainings (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2010). Digital literacy is an individual's ability to use digital technologies effectively, critically and creatively (Eshet-Alkalai, 2004). This is not only limited to the technical use of tools, but also includes the competencies to access, evaluate, and produce information and to behave ethically in the digital environment. For preschool teachers, digital literacy includes the ability to select, evaluate and implement content appropriate to children's developmental levels (Donohue & Schomburg, 2017). In addition, this skill enables teachers to make informed decisions in the use of digital tools for pedagogical purposes.

The basic components of digital literacy include technical competence (using smart boards, tablets, digital cameras), information literacy (selecting reliable and educational content from digital media and evaluating its pedagogical value), communicative competence (communicating effectively with families through digital tools and materials, interacting with learning management systems and digital classroom applications (Plowman et al, 2012), ethical digital citizenship (Developing sensitivity to security, privacy and copyrights in digital environments, Modeling correct behavior in digital environments for children) (Ribble, 2012), creative production skills (Creating content that will contribute to the learning process, for example, digital stories, animations, slides, interactive games) (Bird & Edwards, 2015).

In early childhood, digital tools are not only supportive but also have the power to transform the structure of the learning environment. At the center of this transformation is the digital literacy of teachers (Hsin, Li & Tsai, 2014). The effective use of digital materials for pedagogical purposes depends on the teacher's ability to make sense of these materials and integrate them appropriately (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2010).

Strategies for Improving Digital Literacy of Preschool Teachers

a) Developing Teacher Competencies with the TPACK Framework

Especially in early childhood education where digital tools are becoming increasingly widespread, the TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) model enables teachers to use technology in a way that supports learning by integrating it with the pedagogical context instead of using it aimlessly. TPACK-Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge is a teacher competency model that expresses the integration of three basic knowledge areas that teachers should have in order to use technology effectively. It was first developed by Mishra and Koehler (2006). Content Knowledge (TK) is the teacher's knowledge of the subject matter (e.g., mathematics, science, literacy) that the teacher is teaching. Pedagogical Knowledge (TK) is knowledge about teaching and learning processes: learning theories, classroom management, assessment methods, different learning styles, etc. Technological Knowledge (TK) is the ability to recognize, select, use and evaluate educational technologies (e.g. smart boards, tablets, digital story tools, teaching software). The TPACK model argues that these three knowledge domains are not separate from each other; on the contrary, they form a complex structure that should be considered together.

Composition	Description
PCK (Pedagogical Content Knowledge)	The teacher's knowledge of how to effectively teach a particular subject to students.
TCK (Technological Content Knowledge)	Knowing how to use technologies appropriate to a particular subject area.
TPK (Technological Pedagogical Knowledge)	Knowing how to use technology for pedagogical purposes.
TPACK	is the integration of all these components; it is the teacher's knowledge of how to teach a subject effectively with appropriate pedagogical methods and by choosing the right technology.

TPACK enables preschool teachers to select digital materials in a developmentally appropriate way, to combine technology with play and interaction, and to align digital tools with child-centered approaches.

b) Practical In-Service Trainings

Research shows that teachers' skills with digital tools develop more effectively with practical applications rather than theoretical ones (Prestridge, 2010). Especially at the preschool level, hands-on workshops for teachers and interactive material development sessions are very useful.

c) Professional Learning Communities and Digital Sharing Network

Digital literacy is strengthened not only by individual development but also by a culture of collaboration and sharing among colleagues. Online professional communities allow teachers to discuss digital practices, share content and receive professional support (Trust, 2012).

d) Mentoring and Peer Learning

Teachers with high digital skills mentoring inexperienced teachers helps to spread digital literacy at the institutional level (Lindqvist, 2019).

e) Policy and Management Support

Administrators' support for the vision of digital education is a powerful driver for the development of digital literacy. School policies need to promote digital learning processes.

Collaboration and joint efforts of policy makers, administrators, professional organizations and universities are crucial for the development of early childhood teachers' awareness and skills related to digital technologies. Teachers' knowledge of digital pedagogy should be strengthened in cooperation with all institutions in order to use digital tools in a pedagogical framework and to contribute not only in terms of presentation but also in terms of interaction, creativity and motivation to learn.

Digital Literacy in Interactions with Children and Families

Preschool teachers are the carriers of digital literacy not only through their use of digital materials but also through their roles as models for children in using technology and informing families about digital content (NAEYC & Fred Rogers Center, 2012). Guiding families on digital content selection, screen time management, and the pedagogical value of digital games is directly related to a teacher's level of digital literacy (Donohue, 2015). Plowman et al.'s study (2012) shows that preschool teachers' suggestions to parents about the use of digital materials at home make children's digital experiences more meaningful. Therefore, it is important for teachers to provide parents with information about the educational value of digital materials and provide guidance on the selection of appropriate content. Teachers should prepare a guide for digital use at home and provide guidance to parents on issues such as screen time, interactive content preference, and joint use, and provide guidance on this issue so that parents can choose appropriate content and make arrangements for their children (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2016). Teachers can support family engagement by providing families with educational apps and activity suggestions that they can use with their children through weekly newsletters or digital portals.

Teachers' guidance plays an important role in introducing children to technology as producers and researchers, not just consumers. Research shows that digital materials used with teacher guidance significantly enhance children's learning (Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2015). Teachers directing the time children spend in the digital environment, drawing their attention to meaningful content, and asking open-ended questions to children in activities using interactive digital tools increase cognitive depth (Guernsey et al., 2012).

Areas of Use of Digital Tools in Preschool Education and Types of Activities

In preschool classrooms, digital materials can be used in a wide variety of learning and play-based activities:

a) Language Development Activities

E-books and Audio Stories: Digital storybooks help children develop vocabulary and linguistic awareness (Neumann, 2018).

Audio matching games: Applications that support early literacy skills such as letter-sound matching and syllable recognition can be used.

b) Mathematical Concepts

Counting and Sorting Games: Interactive digital games are effective for skills such as number recognition, grouping, and pattern formation (Couse & Chen, 2010).

Virtual manipulative tools: Tools such as blocks, shapes or abacus simulations help children better understand mathematical concepts during the concrete operations period.

c) Science and Nature Observations

Timed Observation Practices: Digital photo and video diaries can be created to observe plant growth, weather events or animal behavior.

Virtual Experiments and Simulations: Interactive content that allows them to safely experience simple scientific processes.

d) Art and Creativity

Digital Painting Apps: Drawing, mixing colors and creating their own visual products supports children's creativity.

Sound and Music Editing Tools: Children interact with music while experimenting with rhythm, tempo and melody.

e) Social-Emotional Development

Empathy and Emotion Recognition Games: Character-based digital scenarios offer children the opportunity to recognize and express emotions.

Cooperative Games: Digital games that can be played in groups support cooperation, turn-taking and sharing skills.

The Process of Preparing Educational Digital Materials

The process of developing digital materials involves pedagogical planning, content design, and the appropriate selection of technological tools. The main steps that preschool teachers should pay attention to in this process are as follows:

- **Developmental Appropriateness:** The material should be appropriate for children's age, interest, and developmental level (NAEYC, 2020). For example, for a 4-year-old child, short and interactive content that contains a lot of audiovisual elements is more appropriate.
- **Determining Pedagogical Objectives:** The objectives of the material should be clearly defined. For example, the digital material to be used for “recognizing numbers” can be for counting, matching or sorting activities.
- **Interaction Elements:** The digital material should be designed to encourage children's active participation. Feedback, audio guidance, and visual reward systems support this interaction (Papadakis et al., 2018).
- **Use of Simple Interface:** Since children have low levels of technological literacy, intuitive and simple user interfaces should be preferred.
- **Security and Accessibility:** Digital content should be ad-free, safe and easily accessible. Especially applications that can be used offline provide advantages for the classroom environment.

Tools Teachers Can Use to Prepare Educational Digital Materials

Teachers can use various digital platforms to create game-based, audiovisual, interactive materials and adapt these materials according to the individual differences of children. The tools below are presented with examples where teachers can take an active role in both the preparation and implementation process.

Canva for Education

Objective: To prepare visual-based content, activity cards, storyboards, posters, calendars, etc.

Scenario: The teacher uses Canva to design a set of matching cards with images, colors and weather icons for each season within the theme of "Seasons". The cards can be used digitally on the smart board or printed out and distributed in a group activity. They also prepare a “Seasons Board” together with the children and hang it in the classroom.

Pedagogical Contribution: Supports visual learning, promotes concept development, encourages active participation of children.

Wordwall

Objective: To create interactive games and assessment materials (matching, spinning the wheel, filling in the blanks, etc.)

Scenario: While the theme of “Animals” is being covered, the teacher prepares a “Domestic Animals / Wild Animals” classification game on Wordwall. Children group the animal images on the smart board by dragging them to the correct category.

Pedagogical Contribution: Supports classification, analysis and decision-making skills; develops cooperation within the group.

Book Creator

Objective Creating a digital storybook; interactive content can be prepared by the teacher or students.

Scenario: The teacher creates a “Book of Our Class” in which each child writes a short sentence introducing themselves and adds their picture within the scope of the theme of “Who Am I?” covered in the class. Each page includes a student’s voice, picture and short introduction. This book can be shared as a PDF or displayed on a digital board in the classroom.

Pedagogical Contribution: Supports language development, self-confidence, expression skills and identity awareness.

ScratchJr

Objective To provide simple coding and algorithmic thinking skills at an early age.

Scenario: The teacher chooses a character (for example, a cat) in ScratchJr with the children and enables this character to perform actions such as walking left and right and talking with code blocks. The “school going child” scenario is enacted as the theme.

Pedagogical Contribution: Develops creativity, basic problem solving and logical thinking skills.

Endless Alphabet / Endless Numbers

Objective Learns letter recognition, word learning, counting and simple operations.

Scenario: The teacher chooses the letter “B” as the letter of the week. Interactive introductions with words such as “ball” and “banana” are shown in the classroom via the Endless Alphabet application. Then, a game of finding objects starting with that letter is played with the children.

Pedagogical Contribution: Develops sound-letter awareness and supports early literacy skills.

Toontastic 3D

Objective: Supports storytelling, character development and plot development skills.

Scenario: The teacher creates a story with the children: “The Adventure of the Lost Toy”. Children choose the characters, create the scenes and record their voices to create a digital animation.

Pedagogical Contribution: Creating a story structure encourages creativity and language development.

Conclusion

Developing digital materials for preschool teachers and using these materials in pedagogical activities is a contemporary teaching approach that supports the multifaceted development of children. However, it should not be forgotten that digital materials should not only be technological

tools, but also educational tools integrated with conscious and planned teaching strategies. Digital platforms not only support the teaching process, but also increase teachers’ material development skills, enable individualized learning and support children’s multifaceted development in line with the requirements of the digital age. At this point, it is important for teachers to keep their knowledge and skills on early childhood development up-to-date as well as their technological literacy.

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